

Lithium Intercalation in the Anisotropic van der Waals Magnetic Semiconductor CrSBr

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Abstract

Alkali metal intercalation is an important strategy for doping van der Waals materials. Lithium, in particular, was shown to achieve exceptional charge carrier densities, reaching levels at which fundamental electrical, optical, and magnetic material properties begin to be strongly modified. While lithium is known to be highly volatile, its migration dynamics in anisotropic layered crystals remain poorly understood. In this work, we investigate the intercalation of lithium in-between layers of the anisotropic magnetic semiconductor CrSBr. Using exfoliated crystals, we are able to monitor the dynamics of the intercalation process in real time through optical and electrical characterization methods. Our measurements reveal highly anisotropic migration of Lithium characterized by diffusion coefficients that differ by more than one order of magnitude along a - and b -directions. This finding is in good agreement with our molecular dynamics simulations which show trajectories of lithium atoms primarily follow the Br-chains in the a -direction. Beyond that, we find that partially covering CrSBr crystals by thin hexagonal boron nitride (hBN) flakes has a significant impact on the intercalation process, and that lithium strongly enhances the electrical conductivity along the a -axis. Our method offers a new platform for lithium diffusion studies and encourages further research to pursue the fabrication of lithium-doped devices.

Introduction

Lithium intercalation is one of the most powerful approaches for vastly tuning charge doping in layered semiconductors, magnets, and superconductors, and is traditionally accomplished via electrochemical methods.¹⁻⁴ Electrochemical intercalation plays a central role in many liquid phase exfoliation protocols since it often induces bulk crystal delamination down to exfoliated flakes of high crystalline quality.⁵⁻⁸ However, the fact that it relies on complex cell architectures limits in situ studies of intercalation into individual flakes. In contrast, chemical intercalation exploits the chemical potential of the intercalant as a driving force, bypassing the need for a working electrode or cell. This enables direct observation of individual flakes lithiation on standard substrates (e.g., SiO₂/Si) and facilitates in situ optical and spectroscopic characterization.⁹ Since the 1960s, researchers have used chemical intercalation to explore how the impact of lithium intercalation on the electrical and magnetic properties of layered semiconductors such as FeOCl.¹⁰⁻¹²

Another promising candidate for the study of lithium intercalation is the van der Waals magnetic semiconductor CrSBr. In its bulk state CrSBr exhibits a direct band gap of 1.5 eV and an orthorhombic crystal structure of the *Pmmn* space group and *D*_{2h} point group.¹³ Each layer of CrSBr consists of covalently bonded network of Cr and S atoms, while Br atoms are bound exclusively to Cr atoms and arranged in chains along the *a*-direction (Figure 1a).¹⁴ This distinctive atomic arrangement leads to significant structural anisotropy, evidenced by distinct lattice constants along the crystallographic axes (*a* = 3.506 Å, *b* = 4.767 Å, and *c* = 7.965 Å).¹⁴ The relatively weak interlayer hybridization facilitates an easy cleavage of layers when exfoliating the material, resulting in rectangular sheets elongated in the *a*-direction due to the in-plane bonding anisotropy. CrSBr has garnered considerable attention in the past few years because of its anisotropic electronic transport and distinctive magnetic behavior with A-type antiferromagnetic ordering below *T*_N ≈ 132 K and ferromagnetism in the monolayer.^{15,16} Feuer et al. recently reported that Li-CrSBr can be obtained through chemical intercalation with lithium naphthalenide, and it exhibits ferromagnetic ordering with a *T*_C ≈ 200 K.¹⁷ They further observe the emergence of a charge density wave state and demonstrate a substantial increase in conductivity in the *a*-direction due to charge carrier doping. While all studies in the aforementioned work were conducted on intercalated bulk material, the importance of studying exfoliated samples was also highlighted. For example, thin flakes would allow direct transport measurements in the *b*-direction that are hindered by grain boundary formation in bulk Li-CrSBr.¹⁷

Here, we identify optimal conditions for lithium ions intercalation by monitoring its spatiotemporal dynamics in exfoliated CrSBr crystals in situ using Raman spectroscopy and electrical conductivity measurements. Additionally, we show that partial or complete hBN encapsulation strongly affects the dynamics and in-plane anisotropy of Li⁺ diffusion. Conductivity measurements further confirm the feasibility of studying charge transport both in the *a* and *b*-directions, thereby paving the way for future device applications leveraging intercalation induced tunability.

Discussion

Lithium Intercalation in Exfoliated CrSBr

We present a lithium intercalation method for exfoliated CrSBr, schematically illustrated in Figure 1b-c. To begin, we prepare the sample of mechanically exfoliated CrSBr transferred onto an Si/SiO₂ wafer using the conventional Scotch tape method (see Methods) and characterize CrSBr flakes by optical microscopy, atomic force microscopy (AFM), and Raman spectroscopy prior to intercalation. Optical contrast of the flakes is correlated with AFM-measured thickness, and the characteristic A_g^1, A_g^2, A_g^3 vibrational modes of CrSBr at 114 cm⁻¹, 244 cm⁻¹, 342 cm⁻¹, respectively, are confirmed via Raman spectroscopy (see Supplementary Information Section 1). To initiate intercalation, the sample is immersed in a lithium anthracenide solution in tetrahydrofuran (THF), as shown in Figure 1c. Further details on solution preparation are provided in the Methods and Figure S2. During the intercalation process, anthracene in its reduced ionic form donates one electron to the CrSBr structural unit, reducing chromium from the formal oxidation state Cr(III) to Cr(II). As the structure must remain charge-neutral, the excess electrons are compensated by positively charged lithium cations intercalating into CrSBr. After intercalation, the sample of Li-CrSBr is rinsed with dry THF and characterized by Raman spectroscopy again, which serves as an effective tool for real-time monitoring of lithiation. To confirm that lithium is indeed intercalated between van der Waals layers rather than accumulating on the surface, we employ time-of-flight secondary-ion mass spectrometry (TOF-SIMS). The technique described in more detail in Supplementary Information Section 2 demonstrates that after intercalation, lithium ions are distributed across CrSBr layers.

To identify suitable intercalation conditions, we test a range of lithium anthracenide concentrations (see Supplementary Information Section 3). We find that a minimum concentration of 0.2 mM is required to initiate intercalation within 15 minutes. Increasing the concentration further accelerates the process but risks damaging thin flakes. Signs of deterioration can be observed at 0.64 mM (Figure S8). A concentration of 0.32 mM thus offers an optimal balance between intercalation efficiency and preservation of the crystal structure. In the experiment, this corresponds to a concentration at which the initially blue lithium anthracenide solution turns colorless during the dilution with dry THF. Hence, it is straightforward to prepare.

Figure 1. Atomic model of CrSBr (a) with projection along the *a*-direction, *b*-direction and *c*-direction. Structures are generated by VESTA software.¹⁸ Schematic illustration of sample preparation starting with the mechanical exfoliation of CrSBr (b). Image (c) shows the process of lithium intercalation into exfoliated CrSBr together with the schematic representation of lithium anthracene formation in the presence of THF. The wafer with intercalated flakes is retrieved for Raman analysis.

To investigate the effect of intercalation on vibrational Raman modes, we repeatedly intercalate a ~6 nm CrSBr flake with lithium anthracene solution (0.32 mM in THF) in three-minute intervals, acquiring Raman spectra and optical images after each interval, as presented in Figure 2a-b. The resulting spectra reflect changes in the lattice parameters, driven by the insertion of lithium cations into CrSBr. Upon intercalation, Raman spectra reveal two distinct sets of phonon modes, A_g and A_1 , which is indicative of the presence of both intercalated and non-intercalated material within the area we probe. As intercalation proceeds, A_g modes gradually diminish and new A_1 modes emerge at lower frequencies, reflecting the reduction in symmetry from D_{2h} to C_{2v} in Li–CrSBr, as shown in Figure S9.

Within the first three minutes, the onset of A_1^1 and A_1^2 mode respectively appear at 100 cm^{-1} and at about $220\text{--}230\text{ cm}^{-1}$. The A_g^3 mode broadens slightly with an asymmetric low-energy tail. At 6 minutes, the A_1^1 mode intensity increases, while the A_g^1 mode of pristine CrSBr softens yet persists at 114 cm^{-1} , and further broadening is observed of both A_g^2 and A_g^3 peaks. After nine minutes, the A_1^1 mode becomes dominant, and a broadened A_1^2 feature reflects evolving phonon interactions associated with Li–CrSBr. At 12 minutes, intercalation is complete, as all A_g modes from the pristine material vanish, and A_1 modes are fully developed. Extending the time to 15 minutes yields no further changes, indicating completion of lithiation in the 6 nm CrSBr flake within 12 minutes. Despite these spectral changes, the optical contrast of the flake remains unchanged (Figure 2a). We repeat the experiment with another flake to show how the intensity of each mode depends on the laser polarization (Figure 2c). The pristine flake shows the expected polarization dependence for CrSBr with the A_g^1 and A_g^3 mode most intense for excitation polarization parallel to the *b*-direction $E\parallel b$ and the A_g^2 mode most intense for $E\parallel a$. After intercalation, this trend is mostly

maintained, however, A_1^2 and A_1^3 show a weaker dependence and their intensity does not decrease all the way to zero, which could be attributed to a disorder starting to appear within the structure.

Figure 2. (a) Optical micrographs of exfoliated flakes upon intercalation evolution. (b) Corresponding time-resolved Raman spectra of CrSBr flake collected upon intercalation. (c) Polarization dependence of Raman modes for a pristine and an intercalated flake. The dependence becomes less pronounced while the general trend is maintained.

To support our findings in the Raman study, we perform density functional theory (DFT) calculations (see Methods for further details). In pristine CrSBr, the calculated A_g^1 , A_g^2 , and A_g^3 modes align well with experimental values. Upon intercalation, symmetry and peak assignment change, resulting in structure CrSBrLi_{0.5} similar to FeOCILi_x.¹⁰ The theoretical positions of the A_1^1 , A_1^2 , A_1^3 modes show good agreement with experiment (see Table 1). Atomic displacements are shown in Figure S9. The A_1^3 mode is the least affected by lithium intercalation, since that peak originates from Cr and S displacements and its position is not determined with high precision computationally.

Table 1. Calculated and observed Raman shifts related to displacement of selected atoms.

	CrSBr		Li-CrSBr		
	Theory / cm ⁻¹	Exp. / cm ⁻¹	Theory / cm ⁻¹	Exp. / cm ⁻¹	
A_{g}^1	116.2	114	A_1^1	92.3	95
A_{g}^2	241.0	244	A_1^2	206.5	219
A_{g}^3	332.1	342	A_1^3	328.6	331

To get a better understanding of the intercalation process, we examine the intercalation of a CrSBr flake with a thickness of about 50 nm. The sample is intercalated in the same manner as described above and the progression of intercalation over time is monitored. We track the spatial distribution of the A_1^1 mode signal intensity at 95 cm⁻¹ and compare it directly with the A_g^1 mode at 114 cm⁻¹.

Figure 3 shows the optical images during lithiation, along with corresponding peak intensity maps of A_g^1 and A_1^1 modes. The optical image of the pristine flake is shown in Figure 3a. As expected, the A_1^1 mode of Li–CrSBr is absent, while the A_g^1 mode of CrSBr shows a strong, uniform signal (Figure 3d). After nine minutes, the A_1^1 mode emerges prominently, visualized by high-intensity stripes along the flake edges, while the A_g^1 signal weakens, especially at the boundaries, indicating edge-initiated, partial intercalation, which slowly spreads inwards (Figure 3e). After 60 minutes, the intercalated region is clearly visible in the optical micrograph (dark blue stripes in Figure 3c), and the A_1^1 mode dominates the Raman response (Figure 3f), confirming progressive lithiation of the flake.

Figure 3. Optical micrographs captured at (a) 0 min, (b) 9 min, and (c) 60 min of intercalation. The yellow rectangle in each optical image indicates the specific area chosen for mapping. (d-f) The peak intensity maps of A_g^1 and A_1^1 modes collected at corresponding time intervals.

At first glance, our observations presented in Figure 3 seem to suggest that intercalation occurs exclusively along the b -axis. From a microscopic point of view, however, one could argue that the anisotropic atomic arrangement of Cr-Br chains along the a -direction creates a unique bonding situation¹³, which should facilitate an easy diffusion of guest ions along the a -direction. It lowers the migration energy barrier, creating diffusion channels within the structure, which should dictate the diffusion mechanism. Therefore, we propose that lithium ions are unable to enter the material from the short edge (perpendicular to the a -direction). Instead, they enter from the long edge (perpendicular to the b -direction), where they rapidly spread through the diffusion channels oriented along the a -direction, and the intercalation only gradually progresses inward along the b -direction, leading to the observations in Figure 3a-c.

We test this hypothesis in a series of intercalation experiments with fully or partially hBN encapsulated CrSBr. Initially, we confirm that fully encapsulating pristine CrSBr in hBN protects it from intercalation entirely (Figure S10a-c). Then, we cover the CrSBr partly either along the a or b -direction, leaving one part exposed for lithium entry. When hBN coverage leaves an exposed

edge perpendicular to the b -axis, intercalation progresses slowly inward along the b -direction from this exposed edge, similar to a non-encapsulated flake (Figure S11b). In contrast, when the exposed edge is perpendicular to the a -axis, lithium enters and then quickly spreads underneath the hBN covered area along the a -direction (Figure S10d-f), suggesting that Li^+ diffusion is indeed significantly faster along the a -direction.

To get an estimate for the anisotropy ratio of diffusion coefficients, D_a/D_b , we partially encapsulate a sheet of CrSBr with a thickness of about 25 nm in hBN along the a -direction, as shown in Figure 4b, and intercalate it in multiple 30 s to 60 s intervals. After each intercalation step, we track the progress of intercalation deep within the hBN covered area based on the optical contrast. Figure 4a shows how diffusion progresses for a selected area. Under the assumption of 1D diffusion in each direction, we can gain an estimate for the diffusion coefficient according to $L^2 = 2Dt$.¹⁹⁻²¹ In Figure 4c, we present the progression of intercalation in the selected area as L^2 vs. t for one diffusion length measurements in each direction for each time step (further details are found in Supplementary Information Section 5). We notice immediately that intercalation along the a -direction proceeds markedly faster, as evidenced by the steeper slope. Additionally, we observe two distinct regimes, a slow initial diffusion followed by accelerated diffusion, which is likely triggered by a lattice parameter change that facilitates faster ion transport. We calculate an average anisotropy ratio of diffusion coefficients of $D_a/D_b \approx 21.8 \pm 1.1$. Similar anisotropy of Li^+ diffusion has been reported for the in-plane anisotropic GeP during electrochemical lithium intercalation with a ratio of $D_a/D_b \approx 25$.²¹

Figure 4. (a) Progression of Li^+ diffusion within the covered area of a partially hBN encapsulated sheet of CrSBr. A yellow line was added to easily distinguish the border between CrSBr and Li-CrSBr. To indicate the positions where the diffusion length is tracked, two arrows are added to the first panel for either direction, marked a and b . The gray particle seen between 06:00 and 08:00 is a lithium salt, which briefly deposited on the structure and was later washed away. (b) Optical micrograph of the whole heterostructure. The upper part is covered by hBN, the lower part is uncovered. During the intercalation, lithium can only enter the sheet from the exposed area and then diffuse into the covered part along the a -direction, until it reaches the observation area marked by the dashed line. (c) Plot of the diffusion progress as the relative increase of the square of diffusion length ($L^2 - L_0^2$) vs. $t - t_0$. The structure of CrSBr is shown on the bottom-right with the two diffusion directions marked by arrows. The inset in the top-left shows the computed direction-resolved lithium mean squared displacements at 600 K for comparison.

To further clarify the diffusion mechanism, we perform *NVT ab initio* molecular dynamics (AIMD) simulations (~ 50 ps) at four temperatures ranging from 600 to 1200 K on a Li-intercalated periodic CrSBr supercell containing 80 atoms, corresponding to 11% lithium intercalation (see Supplementary Information Section 6). In the supercell, the x , y , and z parameters correspond to a , b , and c lattice axis of CrSBr, respectively.

To quantify the diffusion anisotropy, we compute direction-resolved lithium mean squared displacements (MSD) from the Li-ion trajectories (inset in Figure 4c and Figure S16i-l), clearly revealing the dominance of the x -component. Importantly, the non-zero z -component does not imply that lithium ions are diffusing through the sheets in the z -direction. Instead, it corresponds to vertical ion movements required to access neighboring x -direction diffusion channels, as

depicted schematically in the structural inset in Figure 4c and reported in the simulated Li-ion trajectories in Figure S15b (see also videos 1-6 in the Supplementary Information). Using the time-averaged Einstein relation (see Supplementary Information Section 6 and Refs.^{22–26}), we estimate the total (Figure S17) and direction-resolved (Figure S18) self-diffusion coefficients at the four temperatures, obtaining a theoretical D_x/D_y ratio of 20.7 ± 7.2 at 600 K, which is in good agreement with the experimental value. The large uncertainty in the theoretical D_x/D_y ratio arises from the very small value of D_y , which leads to a significant statistical error (see Figure S18). Above 600 K, D_x/D_y ratio decreases significantly to 6.5 ± 3.3 at 800 K, followed by a more gradual reduction at higher temperatures, suggesting that the y -channels begin to open above 600 K. This trend is also evident in the Arrhenius plot for Li^+ diffusion (Figure S19). The more pronounced change in the D_x/D_y ratio between 600 and 800 K, compared to the smaller variation between 800 and 1200 K, may indicate the presence of two distinct diffusion regimes, with a discontinuous transition occurring between 600 and 800 K, and a smoother evolution of anisotropy at temperatures below and above this range.

Effect of Intercalation on Conductivity of Exfoliated Sheets

A previous study on lithium intercalation of bulk CrSBr crystals found a significant increase in conductivity along the a -directions, while grain boundary formation impeded measurements along the b -direction.¹⁷ We fabricate a six-terminal device to study the direction-dependent conductivity of exfoliated few layer sheets before and after intercalation. Furthermore, we investigate how the properties change over time when the device is exposed to air. The optical micrograph in Figure 5a shows a six-terminal device before and after intercalation as well as after 30 h of measurement. No damage to the flake is visible after intercalation but we can conclude it was fully intercalated from the Raman measurements in Figure 5c taken in the middle of the device. The contact configuration allows us to simultaneously study the effect of intercalation in either crystal direction on the same device; hence, we measure I - V sweeps along the two in-plane directions in an alternating fashion.

Figure 5b shows the temporal evolution of the current measured at a bias of 1.0 V along a and b -directions. Initially, the current is constant, around 0.6 μA for pristine CrSBr in both directions. Upon intercalation, the measurement is repeated in air. We immediately observe a sharp increase in conductivity to around 0.9 μA in the a -direction, in agreement with a previous reports¹⁷. The conductivity then drops over time and approaches a constant value of 0.4 μA , which is below the pristine value. Along the b -direction, on the other hand, the conductivity never exceeds the value before intercalation. Instead, it drops slightly at first and then follows a similar trend of steady decrease as observed in the a -direction, eventually reaching a constant value of 0.3 μA . Time-dependent I - V curves for each direction are shown in Figure 5d-e. In both directions, we observe a nonlinearity right after intercalation. Especially in the b -direction this likely contributes to the initial drop in the current vs. time plot. While improving slightly for the b -direction during the first few hours of the experiment, a nonlinearity in both directions persists and could be the reason why the current reaches a constant value below the pristine material.

We propose that two opposing effects are at play during the initial part of the measurement. Under perfect conditions, Li-CrSBr has an increased conductivity due to additional charge carriers from

lithium anthracenide donating electrons to CrSBr during the intercalation and raising the Fermi-level. Nevertheless, at the same time the process of intercalation can worsen the interface between the gold contact and the CrSBr and introduce additional contact resistance or even the formation of a Schottky barrier leading to the nonlinearity in the I - V curves and reduced current observed in the measurement. Additionally, especially in the b -direction, the intercalation can introduce microtears and new grain boundaries, which explains the observed difference in a and b -direction.

The general decrease in conductivity over time shows that Li-CrSBr is not air stable and will gradually lose its lithium, most likely through reaction with moisture in the air. The third Raman spectrum (30 h Air) in Figure 5c confirms that after 30 h in air the intercalation has been almost completely reversed, which is indicated by the reappearance of pristine Raman modes with only small shoulders remaining. This deintercalation process appears to happen uniformly as both curves follow a similar trajectory for most of the measurement. Further measurements (Supplementary Information Section 7) confirm this trend of gradual deintercalation upon exposure to air.

Figure 5. (a) Optical Micrograph of CrSBr devices before intercalation, after intercalation, and after 30 h of I - V sweeps. (b) Time dependence of current before and after intercalation. Data was extracted from the I - V sweeps for a bias of 1.0 V. (c) Raman spectra of the pristine and intercalated device and after 30 h of measurements (taken in the middle of the device). (d-e) I - V sweeps in the a and b -direction at different times over a period of 30 h.

Summary

Our work demonstrates that lithium can be intercalated into exfoliated CrSBr. This process is highly anisotropic, which is in good agreement with atomistic simulations. We tracked the intercalation dynamics by leveraging Raman spectroscopy, optical contrast, and electrical conductivity measurements and revealed that lithium intercalation serves as an effective tool of

tuning the electronic properties of CrSBr. The ability to intercalate lithium in a controlled manner using partial hBN encapsulation establishes a robust platform for investigating alkali metal intercalation into layered 2D materials, offering new opportunities for tailoring the properties of van der Waals materials for future applications in electronics, energy storage, and quantum materials research.

Methods

Exfoliated CrSBr sample fabrication

CrSBr bulk crystals were synthesized by chemical-vapor transport (CVT) as described in Ref. ⁸ We employed a conventional Scotch tape method to exfoliate bulk CrSBr and transfer exfoliated material on top of Si/SiO₂ substrates to conduct optical microscopy and Raman spectroscopy studies. All studies described in this paper were conducted on the SiO₂ (300 nm)/p⁺ Si substrates. To meet the requirements of the secondary ion mass spectrometry method, we prepared gold-coated (250 nm) Si/SiO₂ substrates by metal evaporation and transferred exfoliated flakes simply by Scotch tape method. For electronic characterization of CrSBr devices, the CrSBr and hBN was exfoliated on polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS) and transferred via the common PDMS dry transfer method. For this the glass slide was loaded into the prober arm of the transfer setup and the flake was transferred on top of a Si/SiO₂ substrate with prefabricated gold electrodes. The stage was heated to 60 °C, maintained at that temperature for 30 s, and then the glass slide was slowly lifted. For hBN/CrSBr heterostructures a slightly different pickup and dry transfer method was employed. A thick PDMS sheet was cut into the shape of a pyramid and covered with a thin layer of polycarbonate (PC) which was obtained by drop casting a 7 wt.% solution of PC in chloroform between two glass slides and letting the chloroform evaporate on air. The PDMS stamp was loaded into the prober arm of the transfer setup and used to pick up exfoliated hBN from PDMS at 90 °C. Subsequently the CrSBr flake was picked up through van der Waals interactions with the hBN sheet on the PC stamp. Finally, the heterostructure was released on an SiO₂/Si substrate with prefabricated gold electrodes at 185 °C. The remaining polymer was dissolved by submerging the device in chloroform for 2 h at room temperature. All transfers were carried out in an argon atmosphere to avoid sample degradation. All devices were annealed to improve their electrical performance (5 h, 300 °C, 10⁻⁶ mbar).

Lithium-solvated electron solution

Lithium anthracenide stock solution was prepared in following way: Anthracene (77.40 mg, 0.434 mmol) is first dissolved in dry THF (4.55 ml) followed by the reaction with metallic lithium (2.00 mg, 0.288 mmol) under an inert argon atmosphere. The brilliant blue color of the resulting solution immediately arises from the presence of radical anions. Lithium anthracenide stock solution molarity is 32 mM. Note that we would like to keep anthracene in excess to make sure the limiting factor is not the availability of anthracene. The dry solvent is ultimately necessary since even traces of water or oxygen will destroy the radical reagent. Under careful observation, we exposed the reaction mixture to gentle manual shaking without stirring until the reaction was complete manifesting a deep blue color and no traces of metallic lithium on the surface. Therein, the prepared stock solution was kept at a cooling temperature of -30 °C. To make the solution suitable for

intercalation it needs to be diluted with dry THF by a factor of ~ 100 to reach a concentration of approximately 0.32 mM. The exact dilution factor may vary *e.g.* due to residual moisture in the reagents, so we suggest monitoring the color of the solution during the dilution process. The point where the bluish hue has just vanished and the solution is colorless usually corresponds to a concentration well suited for intercalation.

Characterization Methods

Ambient condition current measurements were carried out at room temperature with a six channel Keysight B1500 Precision Source/Measure Unit (SMU) in an INSTEC 4-probe measurement setup. Raman spectral measurements and mapping were conducted with a WITec Confocal Raman Microscope (WITec alpha300 R, Ulm, Germany), equipped with a 532 nm laser and a spectrometer with a thermoelectrically cooled CCD camera sensor. The measurements were performed in an argon-filled glovebox at room temperature with a $100\times$ objective and a laser power of less than 2.5 mW to avoid sample degradation. Characterization by Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM) was performed on a NanoMagnetics ezAFM compact atomic force microscopy system in dynamic mode (tapping mode) inside an argon-filled glovebox. Temperature dependent conductivity measurements were performed using the Electrical Transport Option (ETO) of the Physical Property Measurement System (PPMS) instrument manufactured by Quantum Design.

Raman mapping

Raman spectra were pre-processed in MATLAB (R2024a) to enhance signal quality and remove background contributions. Raw intensity data were first smoothed using a second-order Savitzky–Golay filter (`mssgolay` in-built MATLAB function) with a span of 7 points to suppress random noise while preserving peak features. Subsequently, each spectrum baseline was corrected by segmenting the spectrum into equal-width windows and estimating local baselines within each window using a 10th percentile of the intensity distribution. These local baseline points are then interpolated across the spectrum using a smooth spline to model the global background (`msbackadj` in-built MATLAB function), which is subtracted from the original spectrum. For quantitative analysis, the A_g^1 mode was integrated over the spectral range of 104–126 cm^{-1} , while the A_1^1 mode was integrated over 91–105 cm^{-1} .

DFT Phonon Calculations

To verify our Raman shifts and the structure, we optimized the CrSBr and CrSBr-Li unit cell structure, including the atom positions in the QUANTUM ESPRESSO software package^{27,28}, rev 7.1. The unit cell of CrSBr consisted of two Cr, two S and two Br atoms; Li-CrSBr contained also one lithium atom (a similar structure was also proposed for FeOCl-Li¹⁰). The PBE functional was used for all calculations with the projector-augmented wave method (PAW) obtained from the PSEUDOJO library²⁹ with a wavefunction kinetic energy cutoff $E_{\text{cut}} = 50$ Ry and a charge density energy cutoff $E_{\text{cut}} = 500$ Ry. The convergence criteria for the cell optimization were: energy $< 10^{-6}$ Ry, force $< 10^{-4}$ Ry/Bohr. The required SFC convergence was set to $< 10^{-15}$ Ry. Requested k -spacing 0.15 \AA^{-1} , leading to $12 \times 9 \times 6$ mesh, was used. Phonon modes were calculated at the Γ point.

AIMD Simulations

We calculated Li⁺ diffusion in CrSBr by performing *ab initio* Born-Oppenheimer molecular dynamics simulations using a Li-intercalated 80-atom supercell (Li₈Cr₂₄S₂₄Br₂₄) with 11% lithium intercalation under periodic boundary conditions. Details of the fully relaxed (atomic positions and cell vectors) Li-CrSBr cell are reported in the Supplementary Information Section 6. The electronic degrees of freedom were dealt with using DFT within the plane-wave pseudopotential formalism ($E_{\text{cut}} = 40$ Ry, GBRV ultrasoft pseudopotentials,³⁰ Brillouin zone integration at the Γ point, and PBEsol exchange-correlation functional³¹). The ions were propagated for 50 ps using an *NVT* ensemble with a stochastic velocity rescaling thermostat.³² The simulations were performed at temperatures of 600, 800, 1000, and 1200 K using the QUANTUM ESPRESSO software package software package^{27,28}, rev 7.1. The effect of lithium intercalation on the volume was considered by conducting the *NVT* runs on supercells preliminarily equilibrated through *NPT* ensemble simulations for ~ 10 ps. The high temperature regime was chosen due to the low mobility of the Li atoms. Total energies and temperatures during these simulations are reported in the Supplementary Information. Diffusion coefficients were extracted from the Li trajectories according to the Einstein relation.²² Details on the method to extract diffusion coefficients and statistical variances are given in the Supplementary Information Section 6 and in Ref.²⁵.

TOF-SIMS

The Gallium ion source based FIB-SEM and TOF-SIMS system used was composed of the TESCAN LYRA instrument platform on which was mounted the TOF-SIMS analyzer (TOFWERK AG) developed collaboratively by EMPA (Swiss Federal Laboratories for Materials Science and Technology, Thun) and TESCAN s.r.o. (Brno, CZ). The acquisition was carried out at the ion beam energy of 20 keV and current of 260 pA. Mass count from the scanning area was recorder in 200×200 pixels maps with binning factor of 2×2, which eventually resulted in square pixels with size in x- and y- dimensional (top side of the crystal) of 200 nm and 300 nm for scanning view field of 20×20 μm^2 and 30×30 μm^2 , respectively. The pixel size in the z-direction is 0.1 nm per frame.

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Author Contributions

J.S., M.V., and Z.S. initiated and supervised the project. K.M. and Z.S. grew the CrSBr crystals. K.M. and A.S. fabricated heterostructures and performed intercalations as well as Raman measurements. A.S. performed transport measurements. K.M. and A.S. analyzed the data with input from F.D., J.S., M.V. and D.S. G.M., N.M., and G.-M. R. performed molecular dynamic calculation and analyzed the data. J.S. performed DFT calculations. P.L. performed low-temperature transport measurements. M.V. conducted TOF-SIMS analysis. AFM measurements were done by B.R. K.M. and A.S. wrote the manuscript with input from all authors.

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